

A Septic Hermite Collocation Method for Regularized Long Wave Equation

Murat ARI¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University, Karaman, Türkiye

Corresponding author: muratari@kmu.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-4039-5970](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4039-5970)

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Abstract

In this study, a septic Hermite spline collocation method based on the classical Crank–Nicolson approximation is developed for the numerical solution of the regularized long-wave (RLW) equation. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first application of this approach to the RLW equation. The accuracy and efficiency of the proposed scheme are thoroughly evaluated using the L_2 and L_∞ error norms. Numerical experiments confirm that the method is simple to implement and provides highly accurate results for the RLW equation.

Keywords: Septic Hermite spline, Collocation method, RLW equation

1 Introduction

In this work, we examine the following form of the regularized long wave (RLW) equation:

$$U_t + U_x + \varepsilon U U_x - \mu U_{xxt} = 0 \quad (1)$$

together with boundary conditions

$$U(a, t) = \alpha, \quad U(b, t) = \beta, \quad a \leq x \leq b, \quad t > 0$$

and the initial condition

$$U(x, 0) = f(x).$$

The regularized long wave (RLW) equation was originally introduced by Peregrine to represent nonlinear dispersive wave motion. It has been demonstrated that the RLW equation is capable of describing a wide range of physical processes, including nonlinear transverse waves in shallow water, ion–acoustic waves in plasma, magnetohydrodynamic waves in plasma, longitudinal dispersive waves in elastic rods, and pressure oscillations in liquid–gas bubble systems. Furthermore, the RLW equation has frequently served as a benchmark problem for numerical schemes, as it admits analytical solutions for certain sets of boundary and initial conditions [4, 5, 7, 8, 12, 13, 23].

The objective of the present work is to use Hermite septic spline collocation method to solve the regularized long-wave equation (RLW) numerically. This method used extensively for solving

partial differential equations see [1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 22] and references therein. As far as we know, this method has not been applied to RLW equation.

This paper is organized as follows. First, we present the septic Hermite spline collocation method. Then, we demonstrate the application of the method to the equation. After that, numerical results and graphics are presented for some exercises. Finally, we present our conclusions in the last section.

2 The Septic Hermite Spline Collocation Method

In the septic Hermite collocation method, the computational domain $[a, b]$ is partitioned as $\pi : a = x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N+1} = b$, yielding a uniform mesh with step size $h = x_{j+1} - x_j$, defined by the knots x_j for $j = 1, 2, \dots, N + 1$. The approximate solution $u(x, t)$ is then represented in terms of septic Hermite basis functions as

$$u(x, t) \approx u_N(x, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N+4} a_{j+6k-6}(t) H_{ji}, \quad (2)$$

where $a_j(t)$ are time dependent coefficients yet to be determined, k denotes the number of elements, and $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$ corresponds to the local basis functions. Within each subinterval $[x_j, x_{j+1}]$, Legendre and Chebyshev collocation points of order 6, denoted respectively by ξ_i^L and ξ_i^C , are employed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1^L &= 0.033765242898424, & \xi_2^L &= 0.169395306766868, & \xi_3^L &= 0.380690406958402, \\ \xi_4^L &= 0.619309593041598, & \xi_5^L &= 0.830604693233132, & \xi_6^L &= 0.966234757101576, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1^C &= 0.017037086855466, & \xi_2^C &= 0.146446609406726, & \xi_3^C &= 0.37059047744874, \\ \xi_4^C &= 0.62940952255126, & \xi_5^C &= 0.853553390593274, & \xi_6^C &= 0.982962913144534. \end{aligned}$$

This formulation allows for high-order accuracy in the numerical approximation, as the septic Hermite basis ensures smoothness up to higher derivatives, while the chosen collocation nodes enhance the spectral-like precision within each finite element.

The septic Hermite basis functions $H_j(x)$, which satisfy the required interpolation and smoothness properties, are formulated as follows [1, 2, 3, 20]:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{6j+1}(x) &= 35 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h^4} - 84 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^5} + 70 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^6} - 20 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^7}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j-5}(x) &= 35 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h^4} - 84 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^5} + 70 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^6} - 20 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^7}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}, \\ H_{6j-4}(x) &= -15 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h^3} + 39 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^4} - 34 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^5} + 10 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^6}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j+2}(x) &= -15 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h^3} + 39 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^4} - 34 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^5} + 10 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^6}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}, \\ H_{6j-3}(x) &= \frac{5}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h^2} - 7 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^3} + \frac{13}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^4} - 2 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^5}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j}(x) &= \frac{5}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h^2} - 7 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^3} + \frac{13}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^4} - 2 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^5}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}, \\ H_{6j-2}(x) &= -\frac{1}{6} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^3} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^4}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j-1}(x) &= -\frac{1}{6} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^3} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^4}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

To facilitate numerical computation, the system is transformed into a local coordinate framework. For each element, a local variable ξ is introduced as

$$\xi = \frac{x - x_k}{h}, \quad (4)$$

which maps the global interval $[x_k, x_{k+1}]$ to a fixed reference domain $[0, 1]$. This normalization simplifies the evaluation of basis functions and their derivatives across all elements. Consequently, the transformation $x = h\xi + x_k$ yields the following normalized forms of the basis functions:

$$\begin{aligned} H_1(\xi) &= 1 - 35\xi^4 + 84\xi^5 - 70\xi^6 + 20\xi^7, & H_2(\xi) &= h(\xi - 20\xi^4 + 45\xi^5 - 36\xi^6 + 10\xi^7), \\ H_3(\xi) &= h^2(0.5\xi^2 - 5\xi^4 + 10\xi^5 - \frac{15}{2}\xi^6 + 2\xi^7), & H_4(\xi) &= h^3(\frac{1}{6}\xi^3 - \frac{2}{3}\xi^4 + \xi^5 - \frac{2}{3}\xi^6 + \frac{1}{6}\xi^7), \\ H_5(\xi) &= h^3(-\frac{1}{6}\xi^4 + \frac{1}{2}\xi^5 - \frac{1}{2}\xi^6 + \frac{1}{6}\xi^7), & H_6(\xi) &= h^2(\frac{5}{2}\xi^4 - 7\xi^5 + \frac{13}{2}\xi^6 - 2\xi^7), \\ H_7(\xi) &= 35\xi^4 - 84\xi^5 + 70\xi^6 - 20\xi^7, & H_8(\xi) &= h(-15\xi^4 + 39\xi^5 - 34\xi^6 + 10\xi^7). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The first- and second-order derivatives of these basis functions, denoted by $A_i(\xi)$ and $B_i(\xi)$ respectively, are given by

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(\xi) &= -140\xi^3 + 420\xi^4 - 420\xi^5 + 140\xi^6, & A_2(\xi) &= h(1 - 80\xi^3 + 225\xi^4 - 216\xi^5 + 70\xi^6), \\ A_3(\xi) &= h^2(\xi - 20\xi^3 + 50\xi^4 - 45\xi^5 + 14\xi^6), & A_4(\xi) &= h^3(\frac{1}{2}\xi^2 - \frac{8}{3}\xi^3 + 5\xi^4 - 4\xi^5 + \frac{7}{6}\xi^6), \\ A_5(\xi) &= h^3(-\frac{2}{3}\xi^3 + \frac{5}{2}\xi^4 - 3\xi^5 + \frac{7}{6}\xi^6), & A_6(\xi) &= h^2(10\xi^3 - 35\xi^4 + 39\xi^5 - 14\xi^6), \\ A_7(\xi) &= 140\xi^3 - 420\xi^4 + 420\xi^5 - 140\xi^6, & A_8(\xi) &= h(-60\xi^3 + 195\xi^4 - 204\xi^5 + 70\xi^6), \\ B_1(\xi) &= -420\xi^2 + 1680\xi^3 - 2100\xi^4 + 840\xi^5, & B_2(\xi) &= h(-240\xi^2 + 900\xi^3 - 1080\xi^4 + 420\xi^5), \\ B_3(\xi) &= h^2(1 - 60\xi^2 + 200\xi^3 - 225\xi^4 + 84\xi^5), & B_4(\xi) &= h^3(\xi - 8\xi^2 + 20\xi^3 - 20\xi^4 + 7\xi^5), \\ B_5(\xi) &= h^3(-2\xi^2 + 10\xi^3 - 15\xi^4 + 7\xi^5), & B_6(\xi) &= h^2(30\xi^2 - 140\xi^3 + 195\xi^4 - 84\xi^5), \\ B_7(\xi) &= 420\xi^2 - 1680\xi^3 + 2100\xi^4 - 840\xi^5, & B_8(\xi) &= h(-180\xi^2 + 780\xi^3 - 1020\xi^4 + 420\xi^5). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the trial functions and their first and second derivatives at the collocation points in terms of the local variable ξ are expressed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_i &= a_{6k-5}H_1(\xi_i) + a_{6k-4}H_2(\xi_i) + a_{6k-3}H_3(\xi_i) + a_{6k-2}H_4(\xi_i) + \\ &\quad a_{6k-1}H_5(\xi_i) + a_{6k}H_6(\xi_i) + a_{6k+1}H_7(\xi_i) + a_{6k+2}H_8(\xi_i), \\ hU'_i &= a_{6k-5}A_1(\xi_i) + a_{6k-4}A_2(\xi_i) + a_{6k-3}A_3(\xi_i) + a_{6k-2}A_4(\xi_i) + \\ &\quad a_{6k-1}A_5(\xi_i) + a_{6k}A_6(\xi_i) + a_{6k+1}A_7(\xi_i) + a_{6k+2}A_8(\xi_i), \\ h^2U''_i &= a_{6k-5}B_1(\xi_i) + a_{6k-4}B_2(\xi_i) + a_{6k-3}B_3(\xi_i) + a_{6k-2}B_4(\xi_i) + \\ &\quad a_{6k-1}B_5(\xi_i) + a_{6k}B_6(\xi_i) + a_{6k+1}B_7(\xi_i) + a_{6k+2}B_8(\xi_i), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad i = 1(1)6. \quad (7)$$

This representation not only provides a smooth and continuous approximation but also allows for straightforward computation of higher-order derivatives, which is particularly advantageous in the numerical treatment of high-order partial differential equations.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE METHOD

Using the notation $U^n = (x, t^n)$, where $t^n = t^{n-1} + \Delta t$, and Δt is the time step, the RLW equation is discretized using Crank-Nicolson temporal scheme

$$\frac{U^{n+1} - U^n}{\Delta t} + \frac{U_x^{n+1} + U_x^n}{2} + \varepsilon \frac{(UU_x)^{n+1} + (UU_x)^n}{2} - \mu \frac{U_{xx}^{n+1} - U_{xx}^n}{\Delta t} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) can be rewritten as

$$U^{n+1} - U^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} (U_x^{n+1} + U_x^n) + \varepsilon \frac{\Delta t}{2} ((UU_x)^{n+1} + (UU_x)^n) - \mu (U_{xx}^{n+1} - U_{xx}^n) = 0 \quad (9)$$

The nonlinear term $(UU_x)^{n+1}$ in Equation (9) may be linearized by using the following term [18],

$$(UU_x)^{n+1} = U^{n+1}U_x^n + U^nU_x^{n+1} - U^nU_x^n$$

So Equation (9) is discretized in time as

$$U^{n+1} - \mu U_{xx}^{n+1} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} U_x^{n+1} + \varepsilon \frac{\Delta t}{2} (U_x^n U^{n+1} + U^n U_x^{n+1}) = U^n - \mu U_{xx}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{2} U_x^n \quad (10)$$

Now substituting u_m values and their derivatives in (7) to the (10) and rearranging the equation yields the following matrix system of the equations:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{1i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{1i} - \mu B_{1i} \right) a_{6k-5}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{2i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{2i} \right. \\ & \left. - \mu B_{2i} \right) a_{6k-4}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{3i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{3i} - \mu B_{3i} \right) a_{6k-3}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{4i} \right. \\ & \left. + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{4i} - \mu B_{4i} \right) a_{6k-2}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{5i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{5i} - \mu B_{5i} \right) a_{6k-1}^{n+1} \\ & + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{6i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{6i} - \mu B_{6i} \right) a_{6k}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{7i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{7i} \right. \\ & \left. - \mu B_{7i} \right) a_{6k+1}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{8i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{8i} - \mu B_{8i} \right) a_{6k+2}^{n+1} = \left(H_{1i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{1i} - \mu B_{1i} \right) a_{6k-5}^n \\ & + \left(H_{2i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{2i} - \mu B_{2i} \right) a_{6k-4}^n + \left(H_{3i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{3i} - \mu B_{3i} \right) a_{6k-3}^n + \left(H_{4i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{4i} - \mu B_{4i} \right) a_{6k-2}^n \\ & + \left(H_{5i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{5i} - \mu B_{5i} \right) a_{6k-1}^n + \left(H_{6i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{6i} - \mu B_{6i} \right) a_{6k}^n + \left(H_{7i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{7i} - \mu B_{7i} \right) a_{6k+1}^n \\ & + \left(H_{8i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{8i} - \mu B_{8i} \right) a_{6k+2}^n \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The recursive system (11) consists of $6N$ equations and $6N + 2$ unknown parameters. By applying the boundary conditions, we are able to eliminate the two parameters. This reduction results in a solvable $6N \times 6N$ matrix system, which is given by:

$$Lx^{n+1} = Rx^n$$

where L, R coefficient matrices and, $x^n = (a_1^n, a_2^n, \dots, a_{6N}^n)^T$ are time dependent unknown vectors to be determined. Each septic Hermite basis function in this case covers at most four subintervals, which leads to a band matrix with bandwidth six see Figure 3.1. In order to start the iterative

process, the initial vector a^0 is needed. This vector is calculated by the initial condition presented by the governing equation.

Figure 3.1: Patterns of nonzero elements of banded matrixes L and R.

4 Numerical Examples

In this section, we use two test problems with known exact results to analyse how accurate and reliable the proposed method is numerically. The accuracy of the method is also evaluated using two basic error measures square error L_2 and maximum error L_∞ norms:

$$L_2 = \sqrt{h \sum_{j=1}^N |u_j^{\text{exact}} - u_j^{\text{num.}}|^2}, \quad L_\infty = \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} |u_j^{\text{exact}} - u_j^{\text{num.}}|.$$

The RLW equation has three conservation quantities corresponding to mass, momentum and energy

$$C_1 = \int_a^b u dx \simeq h \sum_{j=1}^N u_j^n$$

$$C_2 = \int_a^b [u^2 + \mu^2 (u_x)^2] dx \simeq h \sum_{j=1}^N \left\{ (u_j^n)^2 + [\mu (u_x)_j^n]^2 \right\}$$

$$C_3 = \int_a^b [\varepsilon u^3 + 3u^2] dx \simeq h \sum_{j=1}^N \left\{ \varepsilon (u_j^n)^3 + 3 (u_j^n)^2 \right\}$$

respectively, and these will be monitored to check the conserved properties of the numerical algorithm.

Example 4.1. Single solitary wave The exact solution to the RLW equation (1) is given by the expression:

$$U(x, t) = 3d \operatorname{sech}^2(k[x - x_0 - vt]), \quad (12)$$

This formula describes a single solitary wave possessing an amplitude of $3d$, a velocity of $v = 1 + \varepsilon d$, and $k = \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon d / \mu \nu)^{1/2}$. The wave's propagation is modeled over the spatial domain $-40 \leq x \leq 60$ and the time interval $0 \leq t \leq 20$, utilizing the parameters $\varepsilon = \mu = 1$ and $x_0 = 0$. The numerical

simulation is initiated with the following initial condition:

$$U(x, 0) = 3d \operatorname{sech}^2(k[x - x_0]). \tag{13}$$

Table 1 summarizes the findings derived from applying the septic Hermite collocation method, which employs both Legendre and Chebyshev functions. The resulting numerical data exhibits exceptional accuracy. Furthermore, Figure 4.1 provides a visual representation of the trajectory of the single solitary wave solution for the RLW equation, specifically for the parameter values $d = 0.01$ and $d = 0.03$.

Method	h	Δt	L_2 Error	L_∞ Error	C_1	C_2	C_3
$d = 0.1$							
Analytic					3.9799497	0.81046249	2.5790074
SHCM-L	1	0.1	5.10789×10^{-4}	7.80226×10^{-5}	3.9800198	0.81046313	2.5790074
SHCM-C		0.1	5.14400×10^{-4}	7.80301×10^{-5}	3.9800552	0.81046614	2.5790074
MQ[6]	1	0.1	2.08318×10^{-4}	7.8619×10^{-5}	3.979960	0.8104726	2.579041
TPS[6]		0.1	2.96994×10^{-4}	8.5119×10^{-5}	3.979823	0.8104159	2.578853
IQ[6]		0.1	2.18123×10^{-4}	7.6040×10^{-5}	3.979582	0.8104589	2.578995
G[6]		0.1	2.06232×10^{-4}	7.5355×10^{-5}	3.979846	0.8104508	2.578968
$d = 0.03$							
Analytic					2.1094075	0.12730718	0.3888059
SHCM-L	1		3.20534×10^{-3}	4.43070×10^{-4}	2.1122781	0.13138396	0.3888119
SHCM-C			4.54963×10^{-3}	8.56998×10^{-5}	2.1142600	0.14479677	0.3888175
MQ[6]	1	0.1	4.0259×10^{-5}	1.1922×10^{-5}	2.107167	0.1273011	0.388804
TPS[6]		0.1	6.45907×10^{-4}	4.30236×10^{-4}	2.105547	0.1273215	0.388865
IQ[6]		0.1	7.45694×10^{-4}	4.31517×10^{-4}	2.104109	0.1273011	0.388802
G[6]		0.1	2.87437×10^{-4}	8.3060×10^{-5}	2.106074	0.1272980	0.388795

Table 1: Comparison of error norms and constants for various methods for $\Delta t = 0.1$, and $t = 20$.

Figure 4.1: The plots of Septic Hermite Spline solutions of RLW with **a**, $d = 0.1$, **b**, $d = 0.03$.

Example 4.2. Interaction of two waves For the second test problem concerning the RLW equation, the interaction of two solitary waves is selected. The initial condition for the interaction of two positive solitary waves is defined as the sum of two well-separated solitary waves of differing amplitudes:

$$\begin{aligned}
U(x, 0) &= U_1 + U_2 \\
U_j &= 3A_j \operatorname{sech}^2(k_j(x - \tilde{x}_j)), \quad A_j = \frac{4k_j^2}{1 - 4k_j^2}, \quad j = 1, 2
\end{aligned}
\tag{14}$$

The problem is constrained by the boundary conditions $U(0, t) = U(120, t) = 0$. The chosen parameters are $k_1 = 0.4$, $\tilde{x}_1 = 15$, $k_2 = 0.3$, and $\tilde{x}_2 = 35.1$. These values result in two solitary waves with approximate magnitudes of 5.3338 and 1.6860, whose peaks are initially positioned at $x = 15$ and $x = 35.1$, respectively. Consequently, the larger wave is initially situated to the left of the smaller wave. The simulation is performed over the spatial interval $0 \leq x \leq 120$ up to time $t = 30$.

The numerical solutions illustrating the wave interaction are presented in Figure 4.2, obtained using the aforementioned Hermite spline scheme. Both solitary waves travel to the right, with their velocities determined by their respective amplitudes. The interaction between the two waves took place at approximately $t = 15$. Significantly, both waves fully regained their original shapes after the interaction, which is a characteristic property of solitons.

Table 2: Invariants of two soliton problem at different times.

Method	t	C_1	C_2	C_3
CHCM-L	5	37.9172508543	120.5225776494	744.0569871365
CHCM-C	5	37.9172357037	120.5299525086	744.0570118913
CHCM-L	10	37.9179233337	120.4649085281	743.4582503203
CHCM-C	10	37.9179942258	120.4689959629	743.4582227092
CHCM-L	15	37.9185694486	120.3186589219	741.9047193489
CHCM-C	15	37.9188775106	120.3208055064	741.9047161537
CHCM-L	20	37.9192042267	120.5088058791	743.9314947268
CHCM-C	20	37.9198739896	120.5098735376	743.9315382605
CHCM-L	25	37.9198248648	120.5222139975	744.0713532892
CHCM-C	25	37.9209626300	120.5227186165	744.0713772404
CHCM-L	30	37.9203892813	120.5226402231	744.0756579395
CHCM-C	30	37.9220721085	120.5228691038	744.0756327904

Figure 4.2: Collision of two solitons.

5 CONCLUSION

This study investigates numerical solutions for the nonlinear RLW equation using the hermite septic spline method. The method provide a simple way to approximate solutions for similiar equations. The accuracy is demonstrated through figures and tables, confirming the effectiveness of the method for addressing fractional partial differential equations in physics and engineering.

References

- [1] S. Arora, I. Kaur, *Applications of Quintic Hermite collocation with time discretization to singularly perturbed problems*, Applied Mathematics and Computation, **316** (2018) 409–421.
- [2] S. Arora, R. Jain, V. K. Kukreja, *Solution of Benjamin-Bona-Mahony-Burgers equation using collocation method with quintic Hermite splines*, Applied Numerical Mathematics, **154** (2020) 1–16.
- [3] S. Arora, I. Kaur, W. Tilahun, *An exploration of quintic Hermite splines to solve Burgers' equation*, Arabian Journal of Mathematics, **9** (2020) 19–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40065-019-0237-9>
- [4] İ. Dağ, A. Doğan, B. Saka, *B-Spline Collocation Methods For Numerical Solutions Of The RLW Equation*, International Journal of Computer Mathematics, 80:6, (2003) 743–757.
- [5] İ. Dağ, O. E. Hepson, B. Saka, *A higher-order efficient approach to numerical simulations of the RLW equation*, Pramana - J Phys, 96:30, (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12043-021-02256-0>

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- [6] İ. Dağ, Y. Dereli, *Numerical solution of RLW equation using radial basis functions*, International Journal of Computer Mathematics, **87**(1) (2008) 63–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207160801965255>
- [7] Y. Dereli, *Solitary wave solutions of the MRLW equation using radial basis functions*, Numerical Methods for Partial Differential Equations, **27**(2) (2011) 289–301. <https://doi.org/10.1002/num.20616>
- [8] Y. Dereli, *Numerical solutions of the MRLW equation using meshless kernel based method of lines*, International Journal of Nonlinear Science, **13** (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/766/1/012030>
- [9] I. A. Ganaie, B. Gupta, N. Parumasur, P. Singh, V. K. Kukreja, *Asymptotic convergence of cubic Hermite collocation method for parabolic partial differential equation*, Applied Mathematics and Computation, **220** (2013) 560–567.
- [10] I. A. Ganaie, V. K. Kukreja, *Numerical solution of Burgers' equation by cubic Hermite collocation method*, Applied Mathematics and Computation, **237** (2014) 571–581.
- [11] I. A. Ganaie, S. Arora, V. K. Kukreja, *Cubic Hermite collocation solution of Kuramoto–Sivashinsky equation*, International Journal of Computer Mathematics, **93**(1) (2016) 223–235.
- [12] M. Zorsahin Gorgulu, İ. Dağ, D. Irk, *Simulations of solitary waves of RLW equation by exponential B-spline Galerkin method*, Chinese Physics B, **26**(8) (2017) 080202. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1674-1056/26/8/080202>
- [13] S. B. G. Karakoç, L. Mei, and K. K. Ali, *Two efficient methods for solving the generalized regularized long wave equation*, Applicable Analysis, **101**(13) (2021) 4721–4742. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036811.2020.1869942>
- [14] S. P. Kaur, A. K. Mittal, V. K. Kukreja, A. Kaundal, N. Parumasur, P. Singh, *Analysis of a linear and nonlinear model for diffusion–dispersion phenomena of pulp washing by using quintic Hermite interpolation polynomials*, Afrika Matematika, **32** (2021) 997–1019.
- [15] A. Kumari, V. K. Kukreja, *Robust septic Hermite collocation technique for singularly perturbed generalized Hodgkin–Huxley equation*, International Journal of Computer Mathematics, (2021).
- [16] A. Kumari, V. K. Kukreja, *Septic Hermite collocation method for the numerical solution of Benjamin–Bona–Mahony–Burgers equation*, Journal of Difference Equations and Applications, **27** (2021) 1193–1217.
- [17] S. Kutluay, A. Esen, *A finite difference solution of the regularized long-wave equation*, Mathematical Problems in Engineering, **2006** (2006) 1–14.
- [18] S. Kutluay, N. M. Yağmurlu, A. S. Karakaş, *A powerful robust cubic Hermite collocation method for the numerical calculations and simulations of the equal width wave equation*, arXiv preprint, (2023) arXiv:2309.02439. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.02439>
-

- [19] S. Kutluay, N. M. Yağmurlu, A. S. Karakaş, *A novel perspective for simulations of the modified equal-width wave equation by cubic Hermite B-spline collocation method*, Wave Motion, **129** (2024) 103342.
- [20] S. Kutluay, M. Yağmurlu, A. S. Karakaş, *A robust quintic Hermite collocation method for one-dimensional heat conduction equation*, Journal of Mathematical Sciences and Modelling, **7**(2) (2024) 82–89. <https://doi.org/10.33187/jmsm.1475294>
- [21] L. Mei, Y. Chen, *Numerical solutions of RLW equation using Galerkin method with extrapolation techniques*, Computer Physics Communications, **183**(8) (2012) 1609–1616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2012.02.029>
- [22] A. K. Mittal, I. A. Ganaie, V. K. Kukreja, N. Parumasur, P. Singh, *Solution of diffusion–dispersion models using a computationally efficient technique of orthogonal collocation on finite elements with cubic Hermite as basis*, Computers and Chemical Engineering, **58** (2013) 203–210.
- [23] R. Mohammadi, *Exponential B-spline collocation method for numerical solution of the generalized regularized long wave equation*, Chinese Physics B, **24**(5) (2015) 050206.
- [24] B. Saka, İ. Dağ, D. Irk, *Quintic B-spline collocation method for numerical solution of the RLW equation*, The ANZIAM Journal, **49**(3) (2008) 389–410. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1446181108000072>